

COMPOSITE PATCH STRENGTHENED I-BEAM – LONG-TERM PERFORMANCE AND CONDITION MONITORING

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Keywords: Patch Strengthening, Adhesive, Joint, OBR, Distributed Fiber-Optic Sensing

ABSTRACT

Composite patches can be adhered to metal structures for strengthening. Applying patches is a preferred method over welding metal, because fire hazards are avoided, preventing costly production interruptions in the oil and gas industry or traffic interruption for maintenance of bridges. Composite patches are also light and require little space, making them easy to apply.

Much focus has been put on developing strong adhesive bonds by creating good interfaces and by reducing stress concentrations. Analytical and finite element modeling work has also mostly concentrated on predicting static strength. However, when a real case is evaluated, long-term performance is critical. Knowledge about long-term behavior of adhesive joints as used in patches is still limited. This lack of knowledge often leads to the rejection of using adhesive joints in critical applications.

This paper describes how the strains inside the adhesive joint of a composite patch repair applied to a metal I-beam change with the number of cycles under fatigue loading. The change in the strain field can be related to debonding, moving from the edges of the patch towards the middle. The change of stresses in the adhesive was measured indirectly by measuring the axial strains inside the patch close to the adhesive layer and on top of the patch. The strains were measured with an embedded optical fiber using an Optical Backscatter Reflectometer. This technique allows accurate local strain measurements along the entire length of the fiber, like an array of thousands of small strain gauges.

1 INTRODUCTION

Large steel engineering structures may develop some corrosion or cracks during their lifetime. Repair is usually needed, which is done by welding. Welding can be a challenge when hot work needs to be avoided due to fire or explosion hazards [1-6]. Old bridges are often made out of cast iron or riveted beams and are difficult to repair by welding. Many bridges also need an increase of capacity to meet requirements of modern traffic [7-9]. Strengthening these bridges without interrupting the traffic can be a challenge requiring methods which are easy to perform with little scaffolding and minimal traffic disruption [10].

Laminates of fiber reinforced composite patches bonded to the metal structure is a good method of strengthening without using hot work and welding. This study has looked into one example: a metal I-beam strengthened with a composite patch bonded to the tension flange surface. The patch is bonded to the metal, an operation involving no hot work. The strengthened beam is in this case fatigue loaded in a four point bending in a laboratory test as shown in Figure 1. The stacking sequence of the patch application was an adhesive layer, E-glass woven prepreg ply and 17 plies with ultra-high modulus carbon (UHMC) prepreg.

Figure 1: Composite patch strengthened I-beam.

A challenge for describing the performance of a composite patch strengthened beam is the long-term behavior of the adhesive joint between the composite patch and the metal surface. Short-term and long-term stiffness and strength of a composite laminate are well known. Bonding of strengthening beams and girders with patches has been studied [9, 11, 12] and some design standards and guidelines have been developed [13-15]. However, long term performance of the adhesively bonded joint is still a challenge [16].

Understanding the behavior of the adhesive joint for long-term use during fatigue loading and how the joint fails is important for adopting this technology for repair and strengthening critical engineering structures. A good way to better understand the joint is to measure the stress / strain field at the joint and to monitor changes in the field with time. A novel distributed fiber-optic sensing method has shown good results for measuring strain in the laboratory and for using it as a health monitoring system [17, 18]. Measurements with this method show an axial strain field, which can be compared with stress and strain analysis done with finite element analysis to verify, understand and improve modelling techniques leading to better patch designs. The strain measurement method described here uses an Optical Backscatter Reflectometer (OBR) as an interrogator and telecom optical fibers, which can be embedded inside adhesives and composites laminates.

2 FAILURE MECHANISMS

Figure 2: Failure mechanisms in a composite patch strengthening a metal structure.

Several different failure mechanisms can develop in a composite patch for strengthening a metal component and are shown schematically in Figure 2. Failure mechanisms in the patch laminate and metal substrate are normally a design issue and are outside the scope of this paper. The most widely observed failure mechanisms are cohesive failure in the adhesive layer and substrate debonding (adhesive failure) between the adhesive and metal substrate. They are well known as being the weakest part of the joint [19]. Failure is often a mix of these two failure mechanisms.

Good knowledge of long-term properties is needed to ensure that a patch repair will function over its lifetime. This knowledge is essential for wider use of the composite patch technology in critical applications. Long-term properties of the adhesive joint are very difficult to find and long-term damage criteria are still a research issue. The best practical solution for addressing long-term properties today is to monitor the patch during service establishing whether it is still intact or not.

3 STRAINS IN AN ADHESIVELY BONDED JOINT

Adhesive joints work by transferring shear through the adhesive layer. The shear distribution along the length has typically stress concentrations at the ends of the adhesive joint [20, 21]. It is often referred to as the “bathtub” curve.

Measuring shear stresses is not possible, but the shear stresses in the adhesive joint cause axial stresses and strains in the adhesive and the composite patch. The axial strains can be measured. The shape of the axial strain distribution is quite similar to the bathtub curve observed for shear stresses [17, 22, 23]. Any damage in the adhesive layer of the composite patch will change the axial stress/strain field in the patch.

It is also important to note that the axial strains will change through the thickness of the laminate by shear lag. Adhesive joint models analyze typically the stresses right at the interface. Going away from the interface towards the surface of the patch, the strain concentrations will be reduced due to redistributing stress by interlaminar shear lag. This redistribution of strains is shown in this study, at several numbers of fatigue cycles, by comparing the strain field with distributed fiber-optic sensing (DFOS) bonded to the patch surface and embedded in the patch laminate close to the adhesive layer (between the E-glass and carbon layer).

4 OPTICAL BACKSCATTER REFLECTOMETER

Fiber-Optic Sensing (FOS) is a broad field with many technology solutions. One of the most widely used method for measuring strain is the Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG), which measures local strains at the position of the gratings. FBG's benefits compared to traditional electrical strain gauges are that they can be used in water, they are not influenced by magnetic fields, they can be used in fire hazard areas and they have good long-term behavior. Optical fibers can also be embedded into adhesives, composites and polymers. Embedding the strain measuring fibers can give valuable insight into the strain behavior of a component, not easily obtainable by other methods.

A novel FOS method for strain measurements is an Optical Backscatter Reflectometer (OBR) interrogator which measures the reflected light emitted into the optical fiber by its natural reflective index. This system allows "Distributed Fiber-Optic Sensing" measuring an axial strain field along the entire length of the optical fiber instead of local point measurements. The interrogator consists of a tunable laser source and an Optical Frequency Domain Reflectometer (OFDR), used to measure the Rayleigh backscatter, in an interferometry setup [24]. Interferometry enables the system to measure the amplitude and the phase of the Rayleigh backscatter and with help of Fourier transform [25] the system is able to get information about changes in the backscatter profile and the position along the length of the fiber [26]. The use of multiple wavelengths in swept wavelength interferometry (SWI) enables the system to achieve high spatial resolution of the measurements.

If two measurements are cross correlated, any external stimulus, in our case axial strain, causing a spectral shift in the backscattered pattern can be calculated by comparing with the unstrained reference state [25]. Since the OBR uses the natural reflective index of the optical fiber, commercially available primary coated optical fibers from the telecom industry can be used which reduces the optical fiber costs dramatically compared to FBG. Several tests have been carried out to compare and validate this novel measurement method with traditional electrical strain gauges, FBG and finite element analysis. The results were very similar compared to the widely known methods [17, 23].

Strain concentrations are difficult to investigate with the traditional point measurement methods, such as FBG or electrical strain gauges. By measuring the strain field along the fiber instead, the shape of the strain concentration can be measured directly. Any movement or shift in strain field can be easily detected by the distributed fiber-optic sensing and the OBR system, because of the many measuring points along the optical fiber.

5 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The recommended test setup in the offshore recommended practice for bonded repairs of steel structures DNV RP C301 [15] was used to monitor the strain field and debonding of a composite patch strengthened metal I-beam. The beam was loaded in four point bending putting the bonded patch area mostly in pure axial stress. Figure 1 shows a picture of the setup and it is shown schematically in Figure 3.

The beam was strengthened with an ultra-high modulus carbon (UHMC) composite patch bonded to the metal tension flange outer surface by co-cure. The width of the support span was 800 mm and the load span was 400 mm. The optical fiber for Distributed Fiber Optical Sensing (DFOS) was

embedded close to the bond line between the E-glass and UHMC layer. Instrumentation with the electrical strain gauges and the optical fiber on the patch surface was done after the application and curing of the patch.

Figure 3: Experimental setup for a composite patch strengthened I-beam in a four point bending.

The metal I-beam was a one meter IPE100 beam of steel grade S355J2 according to DIN 1025-5. The bonding area of the patch was cleaned and grit blasted with a surface quality to SA 2½.

The adhesive film SA80 from SP Gurit was applied within four hours after surface treatment. The insulating E-glass woven rowing RE295 from SP Gurit with SE84LV prepreg system was applied between the adhesive film and carbon laminate. The optical fiber was embedded between the E-glass and UHMC layer, before the 17 UHMC plies of SE84LV were applied with a length of 400 mm to 300 mm to achieve a stepped tapering on each side. The whole setup was co-cured in one sequence according to the supplier's procedures.

6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The I-beam strengthened with a composite patch was first quasi-static loaded from 0 kN to 100 kN and down to 55 kN again with a displacement control of 0.3 mm / minute. Subsequently it was running in cyclic fatigue loading in load control from 10 to 100 kN at 2 Hz. The test was stopped several times at the maximum load of 100 kN for taking strain measurements. The first strain measurements at 100 kN loading are shown in Figure 4. No visual damage was apparent at this stage.

Strain measurements from electrical strain gauges are shown as small circular dots in Figure 4 and there is good agreement between the axial strain measurements of the electrical strain gauges and the distributed fiber-optic sensing bonded to the bottom patch surface. If pure tension was applied to the patch and beam, the strain field on the bottom of the patch and inside the patch close to the adhesive layer would have the same level. But since the beam was put in bending, there is a higher strain field on the bottom surface of the patch (except at the outer patch ends) than in the embedded optical fiber. The strain concentrations at the patch ends behave differently and will be explained later.

The OBR measurements of the optical fiber shows a fair amount of scatter at the ends of the patch where a steep strain gradient exists, as can be seen in the plot on the left of Figure 4. The scatter is due to a failing cross-correlating algorithm when post-processing the spectral shift of the OBR into strain data. This effect is normally seen at steep strain gradients [17]. The scatter is smoothed out during further post-processing in Figure 4 to the right, which shows the strain field much clearer. All further plots in this paper are shown with the same smoothing parameters in post processing.

Figure 4: Axial strain vs. patch length at first loading without any debonding at 100 kN. The figure to the left shows the measurements which is scattered. Figure to the right is the measurements which are post-processed with smoothing to reduce the scatter.

The strain field shape shows an increasing strain gradient at each end of the embedded optical fiber. This shape is the expected “bathtub” curve and is well known for adhesive joints [20, 21]. The “bathtub” curve is mainly known for the shear stress in the adhesive, but it can be shown that the axial strain in the laminate next to the adhesive develops a similar shape [17, 22, 23].

The main focus of this paper is to show that the shape of the strain field will change if damage is present and that this change can be measured by optical fibers. The fatigue loading was running for almost 500 000 cycles before any damage was visually detected. This damage appeared as debonding between the metal substrate and the adhesive and propagated symmetrically from each side and moved towards the center of the patch. The debonding is visible at the sides of the patch shown in Figure 5. The side was painted white to make the debonding / crack more visible.

Figure 5: Debonding growth from the left side.

When the fatigue loading had run to 640 000 cycles a new measurement of axial strains was done by the optical fibers, as shown in Figure 6. The debonding from the left outer edge had a length of 150 mm (to the position (-) 50 mm in Figure 6) and the debonding from the right side was 120 mm long (to the position 80 mm in Figure 6). The debonding could be observed visually by the crack on the side of the specimen and was also clearly visible by a shift of the position of the strain concentration in the strain field. This shift can be seen by comparing Figure 4 and Figure 6.

The debonded sections of the patch are expected to have a strain field close to zero, because they are unloaded. However, Figure 6 shows a strain of about 500 $\mu\epsilon$ for both debonded sections. The reason for the remaining strains is thermal strains. The patch is cured to the steel at a relatively high temperature of 90 °C. When the repairs cool down, the steel contracts more than the UD carbon composite patch and are creating thermal stresses [27]. Zero strain is defined by the optical fibers as the condition where the patch is bonded to the steel and has cooled down to room / test temperature. When debonding happens, the thermal stresses are released resulting in apparent thermal strains of the debonded laminate. This effect shows that measuring non zero strains does not necessarily mean that the patch is well bonded.

Figure 6: Axial strain vs. patch length after 640 000 cycles with debonding from each side.

A composite patch would typically be considered as failed when debonding from the edges happens. The debonding could be fairly easily seen visually on the beams tested here. In a real application the patch is tapered on all sides and debonding cannot be easily detected visually. If an optical fiber is embedded in the composite patch, debonding could be detected also in field applications. The patch described here was fatigued beyond initial debonding to investigate how the debonding damage propagates and how it can be detected by the optical fibers.

With an increasing number of cycles, the remaining bond area gets further reduced. At 750 000 fatigue load cycles the bond area identified by visual inspection is between positions (-) 20 mm and 60 mm. The embedded optical fiber indicates a transition from bonding to debonding at the same position as shown in Figure 7. The axial strain in the bonded region reaches a similar axial strain level as in earlier in the test. However, on the right side of the remaining bonded area no strain concentration is measured. This effect is most likely due to a curved debonding front, which reduces the axial strain field gradually. The axial strain field measured by the optical fiber bonded to the top surface is now lower than the embedded optical fiber. This is due to the short bonded overlap which is too short for transferring stress to the surface by the shear lag.

Figure 7: Axial strain vs. patch length after 750 000 cycles with debonding from each side.

After one million fatigue cycles between 10 to 100 kN at 2 Hz the patch has totally failed. This is of course far beyond any acceptable failure. In particular the axial strain field on the patch surface has a constant shape, except for a small reduction at the remaining bonded area, and has no strain concentration as shown in Figure 8. The loss of the strain concentration on the surface to a small reduction would normally be overseen if no strain measurement inside the patch was available. The strain measured on the surface is just the thermal strain, as described above. When using optical fibers or strain measurements in general for condition monitoring, zero strain may be expected for a debonded patch laminate. The data here show that a debonded laminate can still have finite strain.

However the strain field inside the patch has a strain concentration and shows that the patch is still bonded to the surface from 0 mm to 40 mm. This bonded area is not enough to transfer the stress to the surface by shear lag, but affects this area by a small disruption of the axial strain field.

The fatigue test was run further for two million cycles to three million fatigue load cycles and the shape was similar on the surface as in Figure 8. This shows that the stress transfer through the remaining bonded overlap is low and below the level creating further debonding growth.

Due to the low stress transfer the patch does not debond further and it does not fall off. The patch may still look intact based on a rough visual inspection especially when used out in the field in a real application, but it certainly does not strengthen or reinforce the metal I-beam anymore. The optical strain measurements can detect that the patch is not functioning anymore.

Figure 8: Axial strain vs. patch length after 1 000 000 cycles with debonding from each side.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The metal I-beam strengthened with a composite patch remained intact for more than 500 000 cycles. Beyond that number of cycles debonding developed starting from the outer edges.

The debonding grew gradually towards the middle of the patch.

Optical fiber measured with the OBR can be used to characterize the fatigue behavior of the adhesive bond line. The optical fiber serves also as an ideal non-destructive evaluation method for damage monitoring.

The debonded parts of the patch did not show 0 strain, but they developed a strain related to the thermal stresses created during the bonding process. This effect needs to be considered when using strain measurements for condition monitoring.

Damage development showed that the patch does not fall off even though it does not perform its function anymore. Optical fiber measured with the OBR can detect the underlying damage while a visual inspection may not.

A better understanding of fatigue behavior and the possibility to monitor debonding growth should contribute to developing and gaining acceptance of adhesively bonded patches for long-term applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Seventh Framework Program (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement n° 233969 (www.co-patch.com).

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